

Supplementary Data

Database	Search strategy	Results
OVID, Medline, Cochrane Central	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 exp Epilepsy/ 2 epilepsy\$.mp. 3 exp Seizures/ 4 seizure\$.mp. 5 exp Status Epilepticus/ 6 status epilepticus\$.mp. 7 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 8 midazolam\$.mp. 9 lorazepam\$.mp. 10 exp Benzodiazepines/ 11 benzodiazepine\$.mp. 12 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 13 exp Pediatrics/ 14 pediatric\$.mp. 15 exp child/ 16 child\$.mp. 17 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 18 7 and 12 and 17 19 remove duplicates from 18 	2338
Web of science	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 KP=(seizure) 2 KP=(epilepsy) 3 KP=(status epilepticus) 4 #1 OR #2 OR #3 5 KP=(child). 6 KP=(pediatric) 7 #5 OR #6 8 KP=(lorazepam) 9 KP=(benzodiazepine 10 KP=(midazolam) 11 #8 OR #9 OR #10 12 #4 AND #7 AND #11 	227
ScienceDirect	"epilepsy" OR "seizure" OR "status epilepticus" AND "midazolam" OR "lorazepam" OR "benzodiazepine" AND "pediatric" OR "children"	267

Supplementary Table 1 Summary of search strategy and mesh terms used across databases.

Author (year)	Definition of treatment success	Definition of treatment failure	Definition of seizure recurrence after treatment
Bhadran et al., 2018 [15]	Seizure cessation within 10 minutes after drug administration	Seizure continues for >10 minutes after drug administration	NR
Gathwala et al., 2012 [16]	Seizure cessation within 15 minutes after drug administration	NR	Seizure recurrence within 12 hours
Khadir et al., 2020 [17]	Seizure cessation within 10 minutes after drug administration	Seizure continues for >10 minutes after drug administration	Seizure recurrence within 1 hour
Welch et al., 2015 [18]	Absence of seizure before arrival to the ED	NR	Seizure recurrence within 12 hours

NR, not reported; ED, emergency department

Supplementary Table 2 Definition of treatment success, treatment failure, and seizure recurrence.

	Randomization	Deviations from the intended interventions	Missing outcome data	Measurement of the outcome	Selection of the reported results	Overall risk of bias
Bhadran, 2018	?	?	+	+	?	?
Gathwala, 2012	+	+	+	+	?	?
Khadir, 2020	?	?	+	?	?	?
Welch, 2015	+	+	+	+	+	+

Supplementary Table 3 Risk of bias assessment.

Trial ID	Randomization		Deviations from the intended interventions		Missing outcome data		Measurement of the outcome		Selection of the reported results	
	Judgment	Reason	Judgment	Reason	Judgment	Reason	Judgment	Reason	Judgment	Reason
Bhadran et al., 2018	Some concern	No information regarding allocation concealment	Some concern	No detailed information regarding the appropriate statistical method used	Low	-	Low	-	Some concern	No information available regarding pre-specified plan or protocol
Khadir et al., 2020	Some concern	No information regarding allocation concealment	Some concern	No detailed information regarding the appropriate statistical method used	Low	-	Some concern	4.3: PY, 4.4: NI	Some concern	No information available regarding pre-specified plan or protocol
Gathwala et al., 2012	Low	-	Low	-	Low	-	Low	-	Some concern	No information available regarding pre-specified plan or protocol

Supplementary Table 4 Detailed risk of bias assessment for articles not meet the definition of “Low risk”.

Supplementary Fig. 1 Forest plot for rates of failure in seizure cessation after administration of midazolam compared to lorazepam.

Author (year)	Time to control seizure after hospital arrival in minutes, mean \pm SD	Time to drug administration after hospital arrival in minutes, mean \pm SD	Respiratory depression, event/total
Bhadran et al., 2018	Midazolam: 12.05 \pm 12.327 Lorazepam: 15.28 \pm 10.879	Midazolam: 3.65 \pm 1.167 Lorazepam: 7.93 \pm 3.23	Midazolam: 0/40 Lorazepam: 0/40
Gathwala et al., 2012	NR	NR	Midazolam: 0/40 Lorazepam: 0/40
Khadir et al., 2020	Midazolam: 4.84* Lorazepam: 6.9*	NR	Midazolam: 0/23 Lorazepam: 0/23
Welch et al., 2015	NR	NR	NR

* Only means reported from the published data. SD, standard deviation; NR, not reported.

Supplementary Table 5 Qualitative synthesis of time outcomes and respiratory depression.

Supplementary Fig. 2 Forest plot for the need of rescue medication following administration of midazolam compared to lorazepam.